

level was a critical factor: indica varieties gave better results with ammonium concentration of 3.0 mM (Chen et al 1982). One to several globular structures resembling pollen embryoids were observed in the responding anthers. Anther-derived calli regenerated either into green or albino shoots, suggesting that physiology of donor plants, stage of anther development, pre- and postcultural conditions of anthers may be responsible for regeneration of green plants. Frequencies of calli-producing green plants varied in different crosses (Table 2). Chaleff and Stolarz (1981) and Hu (1985) also reported varied frequencies of callusing and green plant regeneration in rice. Callus induction, shoot regeneration, and number of green vs albino plants appear to be under independent genetic control. Anther-derived, field-grown plants exhibited morphological trait variations. Concerted efforts are needed to increase the number of responding pollen and pollen embryos through anther/microspore culture. Use of nurse culture, maltose, and proline may increase anther culture efficiency.

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Long days slow down panicle development of late rice strains

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This experiment probed the mechanism of photoperiod sensitivity in male sterile lines. Materials included wild type Nongken 58, conditional male sterile line Nongken 58s, Nongken 58sr (a mutant of Nongken 58s that is male fertile under long-day conditions), and a transferred conditional male sterile

line W6154s, an indica line which was obtained by a series of complicated crosses originally with Nongken 58s and Zhengshan 97. Seedlings were transplanted 25 d after sowing, and three photoperiodic regimes were imposed: ND, the natural daylength from May to October (13-15h); LD, 16 h day/ 8 h night; and SD, 10 h day/14 h night. Photoperiodic treatments were applied from transplanting (see figure). The parameters used to define the type of photoperiodic responses were days from sowing to heading of main tillers, leaf numbers, main panicle development stage, ratio of spikelet number to

Days from sowing to heading

Days from sowing to heading

Days from sowing to heading at different photoperiodic treatments. Heading dates in each treatment were the average of three plants. Series number of the treatments follows: 1) LD; 2) SD; 3) 5 d LD + SD until heading; 4) 10 d LD + SD until heading; 5) 15 d LD + SD until heading; 6) 20 d LD + SD until heading; 7) 25 d LD + SD until heading; 8) 30 d LD + SD until heading; 9) 35 d LD + SD until heading; 10) 40 d LD + SD until heading; 11) 5 d + LD until heading; 12) 10 d SD + LD until heading; 13) 15 d SD + LD until heading; 14) 20 d SD + LD until heading; 15) 25 d SD + LD until heading; 16) 30 d SD + LD until heading; 17) 35 d SD + LD until heading; 18) 40 d SD + LD until heading; 19) ND. Only treatments 1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18, and 19 were shown in C and D.

Effects of long day on panicle characteristics.^a Beijing, China.

Line	Spikelet number/panicle length		Seed-setting rate (%)	
	SD	LD	SD	LD
Nongken 58	2.83	2.23	84.1 ± 2.7	55.0 ± 11.0
Nongken 58s	3.92	3.21	77.1 ± 3.1	0
Nongken 58sr	4.55	2.94	84.9 ± 4.9	51.2 ± 5.0

^aPlants treated with 7 d SD to induce panicle initiation then exposed to either SD or LD. Data collected from main tillers: average of more than three plants.

panicle length (RSL), and seed-setting rate (SSR). The experiment was repeated three times.

The data from treatments 1-10 confirmed that the LD did postpone the transition from vegetative to reproductive growth of the late japonica lines tested. What was interesting to us was that the LD applied after panicles were initiated (a minimum of 5 d SD treatment) was able to significantly delay their development and resulted in delayed heading (see figure, a-c, treat-

ments 11-18). We found no obvious LD-delaying effect in the indica line W6154s (see figure, d, treatments 12, 14, 16, and 18). Furthermore, when scored by Ding's panicle development index, the slower panicle development under LD conditions was at least one of the major reasons, if not the only reason, for the delay of heading under treatments 11-18 (data not shown).

Not only did speed of panicle development as a whole slow down, but also organogenesis events were affected.

As shown in the table, the LD conditions decreased both RSL and SSR. The lower RSL and SSR under LD might have resulted from the unfavorable effect of LD on both spikelet primordia initiation and male organogenesis.

Our data suggested that LD affects not only the male fertility in Nongken 58s but also other aspects of panicle development. They provide a new basis for understanding of the mechanism of the photoperiod-sensitive male sterility in Nongken 58s—i.e., impairment results in a failure of male organogenesis to respond properly to normal LD leaf signals, a failure that affects nonspecifically various aspects of panicle development. Further research on the mechanism of conditional male sterility, therefore, should focus on the response of male organogenesis to environmental signals. ■

Rice varieties of Kerala as restorers and maintainers for wild abortive cytoplasmic male sterile lines

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Rice hybrids developed and released by research stations and private companies in India have limited adoption in Kerala because consumers there prefer bold, red kernel rice varieties. Hybrid rice programs were initiated recently to boost production in the state, where rice is the staple food for more than 90% of the population. As a first step, we identified restorers and maintainers for the exotic cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines collected from other rice centers.

Three exotic CMS lines of wild abortive (WA) origin—V20 A, IR58025 A, and IR62829 A—were crossed with 43 male parents from the source germplasm, including 26 locally released varieties and 17 elite varieties devel-

Table 1. Maintainers and restorers for WA CMS lines. Kerala, India. 1994-95.^a

Genotype	Kernel color	CMS lines			Genotype	Kernel color	CMS lines		
		V20 A	IR58025 A	IR62829 A			V20 A	IR58025 A	IR62829 A
PTB7	Red	PF	S	S	MO 8	Red	S	S	S
PTB10	Red	-	-	S	MO 9	Red	S	S	S
PTB32	Red	PF	PF	PF	MO 10	Red	-	PF	PF
PTB35	Red	S	S	S	MO 11	Red	PF	PF	PF
PTB36	White	S	S	S	PMK2	White	F	F	F
PTB37	White	S	S	S	ADT36	White	PF	PF	PF
PTB38	White	S	S	S	ADT37	White	F	F	F
PTB39	Red	S	S	S	ADT39	White	PF	-	-
PTB40	Red	S	S	S	ADT42	White	F	-	-
PTB41	Red	PF	PF	PF	ASD16	White	PF	PF	-
PTB42	White	S	S	S	TPS1	White	PF	-	PF
PTB43	White	-	F	F	C043	White	PF	-	-
PTB45	Red	PF	PF	PF	JJ92	White	S	S	S
PTB46	White	PF	PF	PF	Bas370	White	S	S	S
PTB47	White	F	F	F	IR20	White	PF	PF	PF
PTB49	Red	S	S	S	IR36	White	-	-	PF
PTB50	Red	PF	PF	PF	IR42	White	F	F	-
PTB51	Red	S	S	S	IR50	White	-	PF	-
PTB52	Red	S	S	S	IR64	White	PF	-	F
MO 4	Red	S	S	S	MDU4	White	F	-	-
MO 6	Red	PF	PF	PF	Madhurt	White	S	-	-
MO 7	Red	S	S	S					

^aS = sterile, F = fertile, PF = partially sterile.

oped outside the state, during the 1994 wet season to produce 107 F₁ hybrids. The hybrids and their parents were transplanted in the main field during the following dry season in rows of 10 plants spaced at 15 × 20cm. Five pani-

cles from each plant were used to study fertility behavior.

A few florets each from the upper, middle, and lower part of the panicles were collected before anthesis, and pollen fertility was identified with 2%,